

Review Article About Gel Polymers and Their Applications

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Abstract:

One of the important applications of hydrogels is agricultural applications, as there is a controlled release of nutrients from the hydrogel into the soil, which are fertilizers loaded on the hydrogel. A large part of the fertilizer added to the soil is lost through leaching, especially in highly porous soils, in chemical processes, heavy rains, etc. A number of different polysaccharides, such as chitosan, pectin and carboxymethyl cellulose have been used to prepare hydrogels as a fertilizer release system for soil revitalization. Many studies have been conducted in this field. For example, Agaba et.al indicated that moisture retention in a particular soil due to the hydrogel is necessary

to create a forest. Planted Water affects soil properties such as aeration, temperature, nutrient transfer, water absorption and conversion, which affects plant growth. Dimitri et al investigated the applicability of cellulose-based hydrogels in three different formulations, i.e. crosslinked by carbodiimide, as a carrier for sustained and controlled release of water and as nutrients in arid and desert regions.

Keywords: *Polymers, Chemical, Bioapplications.*

Introduction to Gel Polymers

Gel polymers, also known as gels or polymeric gels, were defined as non-fluid colloidal networks, spanning a significant amount of solvent and containing between their chains, at least 10% vol/vol solvent. The term gel initially comes from "galun", amid, because of the pilgrim's flagstones built up from bacterial exudates. In medicinal sciences, gel can be utilized to speak to the thick substance that is

solid yet delicate. A gel can have a gel point where it turns out to be increasingly robust. The effects in the working of a gel can be tuned by changing parameters, such as the quickness or the flexibility. The length scale of these movements is on a par with those of small particles. They have no preferred shape or relative positions.

Polymeric gels are materials having a solid micelle network consisting of a polymer or a

polymer blend. Polymer gels that undergo large and reversible volume changes in response to small variations in external stimuli such as temperature, pH, specific ions, etc., are frequently used as interfaces, in sensing devices, as vehicles for the controlled delivery of pharmaceuticals, in cosmetic products, or in agriculture. There are various multifunctional hydrogels that have been created through the years, for example, intelligent hydrogels or biomaterials mimicking any native tissue. In paradox, nanogels consist of small colloidal particles. Slip link unit involves gel and components of a gel that commands the production. A gel transition at the polymer network involves consumption of flow-producing agents.

Definition and Properties of Gel Polymers

Definition and properties. Gelation is a process used to produce 3D solids in the form of gels, designed to have an outstanding filler capacity, mechanical, and thermal properties. Once filled, a gel becomes a gel polymer, also known as a composite polymer gel. Such novel materials are under the scope of many fields, from pharmacology to chemistry, where they can fulfill very different functions often attributable to the polymeric network rather than the physical state of the media. The shells used in the controlled release of actives represent maybe one of the primary fields of potential application of some specific gels. These are water-containing systems, with up to nearly 98% of water by volume at the composition limits. Worldwide effort is being dedicated to expanding the design protocols for creating bulk gel polymers of suitable mechanical properties for convenient handling (Falcone, et al., 2022; Hu, et al., 2021).

Design and practical applications of gel today meet the need of modern society in polymeric materials that store liquids to release them for drug-delivery systems, sensors, and actuators, energy supplies for environmentally autonomous systems, teachers in the fabrication of devices for coffee machines, capillarity valves and wetting control, membranes in direct methanol fuel cells and batteries progression, surfactants in cosmetic and food industries,

support media in wastewater purification, sensors in chemical warfare detection. In these applications, the technological goal depends on a peculiar coupling between water diffusion (particularly in gels) and diverse mechanical behavior, according to the final utilities. Gels are special materials, and today materials science interests are taken by studying them at microstructural and macroscopic levels (Olvera, & Monaghan, 2021; Bordbar-Khiabani, & Gasik, 2022).

Classification of Gel Polymers

Of different properties. The more highly swollen gels with similar molecular weights would, in addition, have a higher degree of crosslinking, i.e. a lower PBV. Classification of Gel Polymers 1.2 Many systems can be classified in different ways depending on the criteria which are chosen. In the case of gel polymers, a number of ways of classifying them will be suggested in this section and the next paragraph.

The fact that this is possible is yet another indicator of the richness of the field. A possible formal definition of gel polymers is that they are polymer networks which are in a swollen state of some kind. It is advisable to specify the criterion of classification which is being adopted in order to distinguish, for example, chemically crosslinked gels from physical network in terms of reformulation properties. It is felt that cross classification of these systems in terms of their chemical or nanostructure and their functionality would be likely models for inhomogeneous or new systems. This paper will classify gel polymer systems (a) chemically homogeneous and physically sorptive based on a) network topology, b) degree of swelling; (b) chemically inhomogeneous and physically sorptive based on a) macroscopic functional layering. This will arrange the materials to be described into categories based on different properties. It may well be that developments can be traced from, say, slightly crosslinked gels towards chemically inhomogeneous and then fully inhomogeneous gels. Once a classification is available for gel materials, even a detailed one, then systems can be more rationally compared and contractually described referred to various application and

their 'value elicitation functions' (Gu, Zhao, & Johnson, 2020; Sakai, 2020).

Synthesis Methods for Gel Polymers

There are two usual methods to prepare gel polymers, which are the fundamental processes used to fabricate them: (i) the chemical crosslinking method and (ii) the physical crosslinking method. The chemical crosslinking method includes direct copolymerization and crosslinking of a monomer with multifunctional monomers, graft copolymerization with a natural or synthetic polymer and also radiation-initiated graft copolymerization. This physically cross-linked gel is composed of non-covalent cross-linked domains and it is a kind of supramolecular gel. It has weak interactions, which can be influenced by temperature, light, pH and ionic strength. The gelation of such polymers is mainly controlled by the crystallization of the polymer chains or the physical interactions among the portions of the polymer chains.

In the chemical crosslinking method, when gelation has proceeded above 99%, the further addition of an excess amount of multifunctional monomer created crosslinking sites and formed a high-crosslinked gel. The properties of gel polymers strongly depend on the methods used and, as a result, they find a vast number of applications in various fields. The natural products such as polysaccharides, polynucleotide and polypeptides can form gels by themselves in water by the formation of a network. More interesting gel formation exists between natural and synthetic polymers in water. These are biocompatible hydrogels because the polymers used are nontoxic and some can even have some therapeutic benefits. In recent times, smart gels have been developed, which have extensive applications in the biomedical field. Overall, one can say that gel polymers are used extensively in various fields due to their unique characteristics and diverse applications are yet to come up (Daikun, et al., 2022; Deng, et al., 2021).

Chemical Crosslinking

A variety of methods can be used to synthesize gel polymers. In Toman's study, different methods of synthesizing DDS-epoxy-gel polymers were designed and a comparison of their final performances was provided. In this chapter, the focus lies on a summary of the synthesis methods based on the process used to generate the crosslinks in the polymer network. Figure 2a describes this approach. In other words, the label of the nodes in Fig. 2a is the process used to generate them. Based on Fig. 2a, this part can be further divided into three sections.

Chemical crosslinking (CC) is a simple and widely used method to synthesize gel polymers. The process of chemical crosslinking can be divided into three steps by first looking into the reaction type that forms the crosslinking points. A reactive species forms in the first step. This species interacts with the polymer chain in the second step to produce the crosslinks. Examples of this step can be found in the context of thermosets. In the next and last step, any unreacted species are quenched. For the commonly used approach to synthesize gel polymers, the crosslink density can be regulated by varying the stoichiometry of the precursors (in the case shown in Fig. 2a, with A and B as the precursors). The CC method has several main advantages. First, two-end-reactive hydroxyl groups can react with themselves in a straightforward way without any initiators. Second, through proper tuning of the feed components, a hydroxyl-terminated gel polymer can be obtained with full conversion of the hydroxyl groups (e.g., the materials generated). Third, the elasticity and the crosslink density (hence, the mechanics) of the resulting materials are completely controllable. For gel polymers with a high DD, the resulting stiffness is very high, which makes the gel behave like a very hard and jammed granular elastomer (Alavarse, et al., 2022; Gao, Peng, & Mitragotri, 2021).

Physical Crosslinking

As we have mentioned in section 1, most conventional gel polymer formation involves the chemical combination of polymer chains via

covalent bonds, using crosslinker molecules to tie up the system. However, some polymer chains can crosslink via physical mechanisms, not involving the chemical change of the chain structure. Such physical collision or physical protection techniques have been widely adapted in the field of conventional polymerization for the formation of crosslinked or network structures. These states cover storage (elastic) or loss (viscous) types of the Coulomb barrier, depending on the absolute temperature and molecular weight of the polymer matrix.

A network structure might be temporarily formed after exceeding the critical concentration of the limited polymer, followed by competing looping and branching processes in the formation of a thermodynamically stable gel. The gelled polymer still shows a broad molecular weight distribution; however, prolonged heat treatment might even lead to chemical fusion—the healing of the interface to a certain extent of adjacent or prepared cracks. Possible mechanisms consistent with the trend include stress/entanglement alleviation, solvation, surface dissolution, and chemical rejoining of fractured chains.

Other conventional physical processes include cyclic cooling and antisolvent dispersion over a gradient in preferred conformation of the gel matrix, taking as the example thermodynamically favored crystallization of gelled polymer in flowing one and the metastable vitrification in the other. Crystallization is unique in the ability of reducing the polymer matrix, thus driving diffusion-based processes to distribute mobile species, reducing the critical gelation kinetics requirement in terms of temperature and initial monomer composition since nucleation is often a barrier. It can be buildup of a less-than-perfect gel solvent barrier that may exhibit as a permeability.

Offline post-shrinkage occurs gradually after the separable scaffolding material shadowed away and disintegrated, or may be monitored at a reduced rate in percentages. Active radicals may form in air-blood interfaces during the physiological Fenton reaction of Fe^{2+} and H_2O_2 . Hemoglobin is inserted (binding) onto

poly(ethylenediamine)-grafted flat-sheet hydrogels in the form of the expressed hemoglobin, meshing the enzyme generator and its product superoxide to vascular wall components depicted as dash arrows.

Characterization Techniques for Gel Polymers

Characterization techniques are essential for understanding and interpreting the features of gel polymers. These methods are helpful for providing fundamental correlation among physico-chemical properties and actual behavior of gel polymers, in spite of industrial and pharmaceutical applications. There are several techniques available for the characterization of gel polymers such as thermal analysis, swelling behavior analysis, gel strength analysis, drying behavior analysis, particle size analyses, angle of repose study, bulk and tapped density studies, and drug release behavior analyses, etc.

In particular, rheology analysis is an essential tool for the advanced analysis of gel polymers because the rheological properties and structure of these systems are closely correlated. Rheology is the study of the deformation and flow of matter and provides a good platform for assessing the nature and function of the systems in the processing of materials and for solid shape physics. Rheological analytical methods have great potential as a tool to assess the microstructure and physical properties of materials, including complex fluids. The rheological analysis of drug/polymer solutions helps in understanding the aggregation behavior of polymer chains and complex viscoelastic interactions with and without drugs in the systems. The swelling behavior of a polymer characterizes the specific properties of the drug delivery system. Two techniques are involved in this: barrel chromatographic and spectrophotometric. Swelling can be determined from the diffusion coefficient of the solvent. The properties of water in the margin and the interconnected parts can be addressed by the sorption and desorption isotherm technique. In swelling, drugs are compatible with the polymers present in the scheme. Properties such as drug

solubility in polymers are subject to swelling studies.

Rheology Analysis

Rheology is the study of flow and deformation of materials under applied forces. The study of rheological properties of materials provides significant information about fluid motions, heat and mass transfer phenomena, and materials. In particular, in gel formulations, the rheological behavior of the gel is perhaps the most important factor, which dictates its performance during processing and application. A vast amount of literature is dedicated to understanding the control of the viscoelastic properties of gels through various factors such as modifying the chemical structure of the polymers utilized in their preparation, the gel preparation process, or the analytical measurement techniques. Rheological analysis provides a good way to understand the underlying gelation mechanism and, eventually, soften the path for the development of new gel formulations.

Rheological analysis elucidates various mechanical properties of the protective gel polymers. A few popular ones will be discussed in this review. The mechanical spectra, at a constant frequency, provide direct evidence about the polymer branching (or cross-linked). If the polymer structure represents a solid-like network, then at a certain (characteristic) minimum strain (γ_0), the gel network starts to deform significantly and thus is yielded. If, however, the gel network is configured in the form of a loose assembly of long polymer chains, then the terminal or the beginning of significantly large angle of gel deformation (γ_0) does not exist. A linear elastic range with a slope G' (which is a measure of the rigidity of the assembly) is observed before a rapid decrease in storage modulus. Gels exhibiting a significant linear region are described as physically cross-linked gels (Danielsen, et al., 2021).

Swelling Behavior Analysis

Swelling behavior analysis is one of the most important methods of gel polymer characterization. Swelling is the mixing of

solvent with a polymer, with swelling ratio controlled by the solvent quality, temperature, and pressure. The behavior of the gel in the solvent and at the surface is also indicative of water absorption, as in the case of absorbent gel polymers.

Swelling analysis is one of the key ways in which gel polymers are characterized. The specimens are usually dried under vacuum or N₂ purging environment for several hours prior to swelling. They are then immersed in a large excess of solvent to avoid concentration changes due to solvent absorbance, which could alter the specimen morphology during the swelling experiment. For discrete swelling times, usually starting from about 1 minute and continuing in some cases for as long as several days, the specimens are removed and the surface solvent is removed by standard practice. The degree of swelling is reported primarily as the mass uptake (Danielsen, et al., 2021; Richbourg, & Peppas, 2020).

Gel polymers consist of 3D networks, not necessarily completely crosslinked, that swell in certain solvents to such an extent that the step sections between the polymer strands totally disappear. This region of gradual reinforcement is about three times the molecular size of gel polymers and covers a molecular weight range of polymer samples. Clear coil-like entities align and extend along the shear axis during the solvation phenomenon. When this disk-shaped area is viewed with crossed partial wave plates, techniques that toroidal entities injected with a specific volume of solvent are deformed into birefringent films. The structure swells in two dimensions orthogonal to the injection direction, giving a miniature rubber balloon aspect ratio. A compliant polymeric gel where $R > R_m$ will already fill the volume of the container in which it was polymerized or placed.

Bioapplications of Gel Polymers

In the previous sections, several natural and synthetic polymers have been reported. The excellent properties of these gel polymers exhibit possible potencies for use in biotechnological

and medical areas. Herein, drug delivery systems and tissue engineering scaffolds using these polymers are discussed. For application in biomaterials, a gel polymer should be easy to obtain, non-toxic, stable, and have proper melting and swelling points. In terms of applications, the hydrogel systems, mono (hydro-) gel system, and multilayers/hybrid hydrogel composites can be studied. The main advantage of gel polymers for drug delivery and controlled drug release, as compared to other dosage forms of medicines (e.g., tablets, capsules, pills, solutions), is that drug-controlled release delivery systems involve medicine delivery of specific dosage over a time frame from a drug reservoir (Chelu, & Musuc, 2023).

Their applications have focused on the controlled drug release from degradable polymers containing reservoirs of drugs. Similarly, sufficient hydration of the carriers is necessary for successful local and sustained drug delivery. Because of the properties of gel polymers, many bioapplications of hydrogels are possible. Gels are found in some living systems as connective tissues, plant tissues, mucopolysaccharides, and amidated form of pectins (the kind of polysaccharides with intrinsic gelation). They are used in the internal/external ways, as described in endodontics. However, the above natural gelling properties are not the principal goals for hydrogel preparations. This section will describe the possible bioapplications of gel polymers. The development of suitable biomaterials represents a key factor for tissue engineering. A bioengineered scaffold should meet several conditions, which are as follows: Proper biodegradability. Sufficient mechanical properties. Ability to support cell growth and differentiation with regard to cell type and tissue. One of the methods for obtaining a bioengineered scaffold is the application of processed patternable suitable materials. The ideal biomaterial should closely resemble that of the native ECM of interest for a specific tissue scaffold, not be toxic, exhibit optimal mass, and mechanical and biochemical qualities for tissue engineering. For biomedical applications, polysaccharides, the natural polymers, exhibit

some advantages in that, either as raw materials or as their derivatives, they are less expensive and are readily available and can be obtained in high yields from nature. Moreover, they are water-soluble, have useful hydrophilic properties, and immune responses which make them useful for drug delivery systems. Therefore, we expect the opportunities of developing novel soft gel polymers for bioapplications in the near future (Bolívar Monsalve, et al., 2021).

Drug Delivery Systems

Gel polymers have found numerous applications in the development of translational drug delivery systems for improving therapeutic outcomes. Controlled drug delivery refers to the system in which the site of absorption, initial concentration, and release rate of the drug are controlled. This kind of system is designed in a manner that insignificant fluctuation in plasma concentration of the drug can be attained with minimum side effects. On the other hand, targeted drug delivery system refers to the natural and clinical systems in which preliminary steps of drug treatment processes in humans and animals are significantly sophisticated and enhanced.

Both approaches have gained immense importance in the drug delivery research as they provide sustained administration of the drug based on the following processes: (i) an in situ gelation of the polymer in the presence of physiological fluid (also known as in situ forming implants); (ii) as mucoadhesive gel that sticks to the gastric or vaginal mucosae; (iii) as a liquid administration system that undergoes gelation on contact with mucosal surfaces; (iv) as a film that adheres to the skin; or (v) as a solid rod or such-shaped device that slowly biodegrades, releasing drug over several weeks or months inside the body. Novel stimuli-sensitive injectable in-situ forming systems are designed to exhibit reversibly sol-gel transitions (either reversible or irreversible, depending on the specific applications). Site-specific, time-controlled delivery by sustained and prolonged drug release on the site of application will lead to a significantly enhanced therapeutic index.

Modular design and construction of gel-forming polymer architectures (many of which are biodegradable, thus avoiding another surgery for removal) is a pivotal area in the current drug delivery research (Vigani, et al., 2020).

Tissue Engineering Scaffolds

Tissue engineering, a major application of gel polymers, is the combination of architecture, engineering, and material science principles to develop a biological substitute that could help maintain, improve, or restore tissue function. This can be utilized for patients suffering from tissue disorders. Gel polymers have been used as replacement alternatives for artificial scaffolds in tissue engineering due to their biological and chemical properties, as well as their ability to incorporate diverse types of cells and drugs. They are also used as biopolymers. Along with cells and biomolecules, gels can act as a seed bed, allowing cells to disperse and undergo growth, proliferation, and differentiation in vitro.

One of the important functions of scaffolds in tissue engineering is to provide a physical structure for tissue regeneration. Hydrogels, as insoluble heteropolymer networks, can rigidify under biological circumstances while maintaining unchanged water content in the gels. As a result, they are responsible for the "porous" physical appearance of the scaffolds. The combination of gel polymers can exploit complementary properties that address the limitations of individual materials. Gelatin and chitosan, when combined, form a crosslinked, nano-fibrous construct. This may satisfy the strength requirements of some tissue-engineering applications while maintaining cell-adhesive properties and degradation rate. This could be used to compensate for the weaknesses of process-based systems. The cells are then continuously dispensed in the hydrogel prior to crosslinking (Quan, Kisailus, & Meyers, 2020).

Environmental Applications of Gel Polymers

Gel polymers have been extensively explored in the fields of consumer, medical, and industrial products. In addition to this, gel polymers are

often associated with recent green technological developments and are used in many industrial applications. Because of the developing environmental concerns, many researchers are looking for alternatives to toxic chemicals that deteriorate the quality of life. Gel polymers can certainly be part of the solution to overcome some of the environmental problems that we face. Some of the promising applications of gel polymers are for water purification technologies and soil stabilization. The applications that will be discussed in this section are the removal of inorganic compounds, such as heavy metal ions and fluoride anions, from natural waters. It was reported that a new gel polymer, Gel-p-MAA-APTES, was capable of removing the arsenic anions from multi-anionic systems. Similarly, another gel polymer was also shown to have potential at removing the radioactive ⁹⁰Strontium (⁹⁰Sr) and ¹³⁷Cesium (¹³⁷Cs) from seawater.

Alternatively, for water treatments, high surface area gel polymers were prepared for the rapid removal of toxic metal wearable ions. Thermoresponsive poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) gel beads were utilized in the development of a controllable release system for herbicide formulation. In this study, the hampered release of the herbicide under warmer conditions is demonstrated. Herbicide is a chemical agent that is known to reduce the biodiversity of agricultural soil. It is essential to develop a system that can slow down the release of the herbicide into agricultural water. To the best of our knowledge, no gel polymer for the removal of herbicides has been reported before. As previously mentioned, at least 90–99% of herbicides applied to crops may get absorbed by the soil. Consequently, even a weakly absorbing herbicide can cause a serious impact on the environment. It is therefore believed that conducting breakthrough research using a pH-responsive gel polymer to remediate a weakly absorbed herbicide from an aqueous environment can open new vistas in the field of environmental science and engineering. The potential of the newly developed gel polymer in environmental applications is highlighted by its high removal efficiency of the weakly absorbing

triazine herbicide at pain as a case study application (Utzeri, et al., 2021).

Water Purification Technologies

In recent years, society and scientists have been interested in water cleaning technologies. However, it is still a demanding task due to restrictions on energy consumption and operational issues. Plants for water purification employ different-scale technologies based on various methods for removing contaminants and impurities. At the same time, environmental pollution has increased due to the vast development of industry and urbanization, resulting in an increase in chemical production and consumption and, as a result, a serious problem with water purity. Furthermore, the global shortage of drinking water is leading to an increasing need for urgent cost-effective, scalable, durable, and efficient technologies worldwide. Therefore, it is an opportune time to review the interest in gel polymers research to address the aforementioned issues. This contribution focuses on the applications of gel polymers in science and technologies, specifically on the removal of chemical, THMs, and heavy metal pollutants from water industrial waste.

The current chapter reviews published papers on gel polymers in technologies for treating drinking, dam, river, sea, and ground waters (even injected ones) that contribute significantly to water sciences, chemical and material science, nanotechnologies, environment, and health-related research. Additionally, the chapter emphasizes water purification costs and constraints, including the need for pressurized operating systems. Recently, the development of practical reactive gel polymers for 'in-line' water purification technology has been introduced, which provides a convenient platform for simultaneous treatment of water contamination, including pathogens, minerals, odors, organics, and heavy metals. has recently presented the more recent capacity of these gel polymers combined at high temperature and salinity during desalination water cleaning. The capacity characteristics of gel polymers needed for process control and technological scalability are

similar to those reported for the removal of hydrophilic and hydrophobic markers and other contaminants from various resource and wastewater supplies. This chapter highlights and reviews gel polymers in studies of water science and technologies in non-pressurized water purification systems for capacity and catalyst technologies, providing cost-effective and low environmental impact reactions, including scale and broad-spectrum treatment, with known pathogen (bacteria and virus) log kill and removal, including a wide range of unknown pathogens and most biomolecular and reactive contaminants and toxins. Water saving is a very important additional economic and environmental benefit of the highly efficient water cleaning capability of the gel polymers addressed. Biofouling management is a very important application of gel polymers in MBR (membrane bioreactors) that may be enabled by funding the technology for its related environmental and water-saving benefits. It is also related to the use of sorbent and/or catalyst depicting gels along with POU (point of use) and POE (point of entry) technology development. Gel polymers can advantageously be used in mining and metallurgy in various stages and processes of ore treatment and reuse (Lei, Ang, & Wu, 2023; Zaquen, et al., 2020).

Soil Stabilization

Soil stabilization is a method used to enhance and improve the strength and stability of the soil. Adding gel polymers to the soil is one of the most recent approaches used for soil stabilization. The use of hydrogels to improve the swelling properties and gel strength has been a growing field. Composite hydrogels are capable of reducing the cracking and failure of both fine and coarse soils and have the potential for use in the field of geotechnical engineering.

In addition to using hydrogels to improve the soil itself, a blend of hydrogels and Coir can be used to address some of the problems associated with the soil's seepage and water retention. The use of gel polymer in the field of soil science contributes to the land sustainability. It reduces the amount of erosion, suppresses dust that causes air pollution, uses the underground poor

materials in the construction process, and can be applied in remediating the soil or the affected soil by oil, chemical wastes, which costs millions to decontaminate (Fatehi, et al., 2021).

Gel polymers and nanomaterials are very new to the many fields of engineering, in particular, civil and construction engineering. This process was known as soil stabilization using the hydrogels or new chemical compounds or known as polymer. This technology not only uses virgin soil but also utilizes local or conditional soil for construction. These polymers are expected to improve the bearing capacity and tensile physical properties of the mixed with soil at least double. In this project, the physical properties of soils such as tensile strength and bearing capacity are being studied. In addition, some other physical strength properties are also determined, such as plasticity index, group index, organic content, moisture absorption capacity, and swelling.

Conclusion

Industrial and Consumer Product Applications of Gel Polymers

Gel polymers are of great importance to the personal care industry, providing rheology control in formulations to improve texture, suspension, and stability of the product. Deodorants, toothpastes, and skin lotions are well-known examples of gels. Polymers used in personal care products include associative thickeners, polyacrylates, and polyelectrolytes.

Gel polymers are added to foods to enhance the physical properties, texture, appearance, and control of the release of flavor. The hydrocolloids used in foods represent a small percentage of traditional agriculture and marine. The majority of natural polymers are derived from seaweeds. Agar and carrageenan are important components in the formation of food gels. On the other hand, alginate is less gelatinized and is employed mainly for thickening purposes, such as yogurt. In the food industry, many of the emulsions and alterations of gel liquids are utilized in the production of sauces, ketchups, mayonnaise, and salad dressings. A new use for gel polymers in the food

area is in the development of nutrient or drug delivery systems. These systems dissolve in the mouth while delivering drugs or nutrients. The gel polymers have therefore helped in the development of extensions of structured food items under a range of presentations, including pastries, chocolates, cream and fillings, and sugars. They have also been used in the development of liquid-filled sweets (Teixeira-Costa, & Andrade, 2021; Carina, et al., 2021).

Gel polymers are used in diverse areas for demand in all kinds of industrial activities covering cleaning, benefits, and inflammation. Examples include firefighting products, automotive lubricating fuel additions, and drilling fluids. They may be used as release and pain management agents as they are used in a wide variety of ointments, creams, and jellies. Incorporated with skin-benefiting botanical ingredients, the gels help to retain moisture, which can have a desirable long-term impact on the signs of aging. Sugar-free diets may provide some relief to a patient who suffers muscle or joint pain. Many people have found some relief from muscle pain by eating a clay diet. Mustard packs are useful first aid for minor swelling and pain. A mustard pack is prepared by mixing dry, roasted mustard flower with proper water, putting it in a bandage, then folding the bandage in layers to add a layer of thin muslin at one end. Then apply and cover with a cold towel. Use for 20 to 60 minutes. A mustard pack can be given for body pain, back pain, asthma, bronchial pain, paralysis of the spine, and joint pain (Junjunan, et al., 2021; Mähling, Schimmel, & Placek, 2020).

Personal Care Products

Personal care products are a broad category of consumer goods that are used to maintain personal hygiene and clean, enhance, and protect one's appearance. Personal care products are very important in everyone's day-to-day life. A range of formulations based on materials like gel, foams, microemulsions, etc. require the usage of gel-forming polymers that help to formulate and perform products used for daily skin and hair care.

In skin care applications, they are used in anti-aging creams, sun-care formulations, after-sun

formulations like gels and lotions, skin protectants, hand sanitizers, etc. In fact, in baby lotions and creams, they are used as well as in toothpaste to get better paste regulation on toothbrushes. In hair care applications, they are used in shampoos, gels, mousses, and detangling formulations, etc.

The term "gel polymers" means that they can form a gel from the liquid under suitable processing conditions and may transform the gel back to the liquid if any further change in the processing conditions takes place (Dai. Et al., 2021; Lin, Kelly, & Miao, 2020).

Gel polymers play an important role in the design and performance of personal care products, and this work has increased in the development and trial of new ingredients, as well as innovative products such as sunscreen mousse, cream, and shampoo. Gels are highly desirable due to their less liquid leakage compared to the corresponding liquid soap. Additionally, entangled polymer chains create minor leakage of the liquid unlike the loose networks and give thicker and more charged flowing, which is important when the product will increase in viscosity or spreading deviation.

Filled polymers with gelling properties can be applied in hand sanitizers, face wash, hair gel, etc. Gel polymers have the potential to form a gel in combination with a surfactant solution. Sunscreen exhibits enhanced spreadability and longer durability when combined with gel-forming substances. High concentrations of ionic surfactants contained in the gel give improved spumeability and microemulsibility compared to the water-alcohol liquid sample due to lowering of the interfacial tension (Nadia. Et al., 2023; Dutta, Goyal, & Kumar Sharma, 2022).

Food Industry

Gel polymers have many applications in the food industry. They are mainly used as additives to obtain better texture and improved stability. Proteins and polysaccharides are the most preferred compounds when forming gel polymers. The delicacy of gels makes them perfect for biotechnological applications, as they improve the final product quality. Gel polymers

are playing an important role in improving the overall quality and nutritional content of food products. Furthermore, they are an important factor in the development of new food products as they can prevent the movement of several molecules in the product, such as gas or product volume changing agents. Gel polymers can be processed into ready-to-use food products or processed into profiles to be used for various purposes (Bealer, et al., 2020; Yang, et al., 2021).

Different types of gel polymers are considered proteins and polysaccharides. Gelation proteins can be produced from meat, milk, fish, eggs, and grains. The formed gels are stronger, but they may not be heat stable, and their characteristics depend on the proteins used. Protein gelation is usually achieved using factors including heating, pH change, and mechanical shear and enzymatic treatment. Polysaccharide gelation occurs through temperature and/or chemical changes, and it usually does not require the addition of ions for the gel. A gel or polymer forming with a similar mass distribution usually does not dissolve in the product. Such a material does not disrupt the contact between the formed sheets into one sheet structure, thus significantly reducing the movement of several substances such as product volume changing agents, gases, etc. For example, gelatin or carrageenan forms a network containing polysaccharides and proteins with the water-soluble portion (hydrosoluble) which interacts with the gel solution, but the formed gels do not mix or dissolve in the distribution through the bulk (Tang, et al., 2023; Gräfenhahn, Karbstein, & Emin, 2020).

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